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The Concept of Religiosity at Islamic Education in Modern Era

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ABSTRACT

Study on the idea of religiosity of Islamic schooling in the contemporary era. The concern that tends to be in the modern era is that all the inclined protagonists are working comprehensive and individual. Wherever Islamic education should enhance individual quality with a value-added component, that means the definition of religiosity to overcome the inclination of society; the new generation would create the ethical, firm conviction, individual energy, and intellectual research. What is the definition of religiosity in modern-day Islamic education that has a strong relationship? The objective of this research is to find out. What is the definition of religiosity for Islamic study in the modern era? The approach used is bibliography analysis and the qualitative process, the significance and interpretation of religiosity in Islamic schooling in the light of modern-era new globalization since faith is a way of life that includes laws that must be followed in order to be allowed to alter and convert into an insane lifestyle.

INTRODUCTION

Human beauty resides not only in its shape but also in the ability retained, that is, the thinking mechanism not exhibited by individual species. The abundant enough opportunities to understand everything research, make human beings unique species. A very nuanced awareness is what allows us the best in life to control life. Education is a part of what God orders, a cycle that starts from birth before death takes place in Islam to achieve the dignity of life, where the cycle of contact between studying and teaching takes place. Therefore, it can be inferred that schooling is an operation carried out by human beings to alter the mind-set for the better through awareness and ethical character by behavioral improvement. The method of modifying human actions in order to become improved human beings is one of the meanings of learning, that is, from what is not now understood, from a little to a ton to obtain riches of wisdom that can be. The philosophy of Islamic religious education in the modern age is still focused on the Quran, so the Sunnah is a vital topic to learn since the principle of religiosity in Islamic religious education must be explicitly taught to students how to act well with their instructors, and the teaching content is a component that can not be segregated from the theological context of Islamic religious education. What needs to be implemented or stopped in understanding the definition of religiosity in Islamic religious education, moreover, this aim includes philosophical justification that is to glorify God. That is because the hero is veiled among conservative human beings. Too crucial because there are very few citizens who have the quality.

If there are not a lot of religious people, is menage scientifically religious? Religiosity is originated from the English language 'faith,' which means faith. Instead, religiosity is defined as a person's theological concept linked to the religious structure of beliefs and relevant rules. In this period of the modern world, there are several variations in the interpretation of religion. There are several discrepancies in one's religion in Islamic religion that the root is mainly non-Quran and h. In this

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situation, there is also a social tradition, one of the systematic value-added schooling methods. Because there are values, role models, and the preparation of young people in their realization, they can be independent by teaching and facilitating moral decision-making in a responsible manner and other life skills. It should also be seen that religious values can be understood both within the school and society. Is there an effort to internalize religious values among students? In truth, a seed of faith has been planted in the human soul, which can sense God's presence. This flavor is usual. That is what is called the divine impulse. Religious views are God's values or teachings.

Research question

1. What is the relationship between the concepts of religiosity with Islamic education in the modern era?
2. Are there any good or bad impacts on the light of Islamic education in the modern era?
3. Is there a role for religion in modern society?

Research objective

1. To examine the relationship between the concepts of religiosity with convulsive behavior for students at the university
2. It can explain the sound or adverse effects of Islamic education in the modern era.
3. Know the role of religion that exists in society in the modern era.

Discussion

This study was conducted to show that the concept of religiosity for the majority of students generally has a kind nature of religiosity because it is demonstrated by the motivation to learn Islamic education which also demonstrates that most students have a significant relationship between religiosity and the motivation of Islamic religious education for participating students. The association between the idea of religiosity and Islamic theological education is attributed to the reality that religiosity is reflected in different areas of human life. That is, religious practices do not exist. In contrast, anyone does not only pray, but even when performing certain things such as studying, because faith is a structure that has other aspects including religion, a network of images, views, principles, and actions, many of which are based around topics that are most important to existence. The appropriate interpretation of religious principles about Islamic religious education can shape individuals who tend to be kings, commit, accountability, ambition, integrity, enthusiasm, and tolerance. Besides the positive or negative influence of the idea of religiosity on Islamic religious schooling, it does not have an unfortunate effect since viewed from theology, and research is two aspects that can not be segregated from each other. As what is learned by faith rarely contributes to a destructive attitude, since the philosophy of Islam is beautiful. There is also a need to recognize the definition of full religiosity for Islamic theological education that comes from the Qur'an and the Sunnah so that Islamic teachings that are contradictory to Islamic philosophy are no longer corrupted.

The role of faith in modern society's life in the rapid growth of this period is a very accessible opportunity to establish a Muslim community. Constructing the importance of goodness at that time, the meaning of secular monotheism of acceptance was to accept Islam amid the Javanese culture. Through the same world, culture is turned into an ideology that interprets faith through people's lives. Consequently, a religion that evolves in science, particularly Islam, has a fundamental existence in human life. In the background of the culture, however, cultural influences may emerge in religion. There is a probability of faith and secular truth in Islam, where there is no fact of spiritual reality. Religion must evolve by adopting a culture that adapts itself to the climate. Thus, the development of religion in society always appears to be the building blocks and structures of human thought. At this time, the community has made interpretations of religious teachings. However, in the religion, religious law, and lifestyle of the community, this is unique in this religious phenomenon.

It can be seen from a peculiar or odd perspective in contemporary society, as religious views appear contradictory. This faith, which was historically a rule in Muslim existence, is the product of modern

days, of all-new societies, from various kinds of new forces, which come or are present, since socio-cultural influences seem to be an issue in things, and, in the meantime, social existence and everyday life, the com. However, not everyone is called a modern society that forgets the old religious and cultural values of moral and social values. A progressive community with a rational mind, pursuing new trends with demands that are successful and good for their lives, and yet pay heed to their adverse effects. Symbolic public life is not thinking of going forward in life. The human culture of general requires a combination of desire and sanctity. Does the interaction of faith play a part in the alternate course of life in the mind in a martial question? Religion in existence as a person has the purpose and position of standards in the two systems. Then the norms that encourage behavior and behavior that will be consistent with the religious beliefs adopted and strengthen religion by correctly understanding monotheism and maintaining the "aqeedah" that exists in each person.

So religion is significant in life, so people need religion because, without religion, a person has no basis or direction. Above everything, faith is the most crucial guidance and reference in any human being on this planet, a pioneer of religious existence. Most of the world's universities have institutions in training and certification that have a solid religious or religious foundation. Nearly all the practices carried out at this university are linked to faith, as the scope of learning from the campus's extracurricular practices and the everyday life of its students at the university level often allow new students beyond the city to stay in the girls' dormitory. Throughout the everyday life of a female dormitory, including worshiping or participating throughout a congregation, this hostel also offers a place with services and services for the recitation with 'Tafizul Quran' or other religious practices. This is because environmental factors play a very important role in the formation of students' convulsive behavior, which is why many universities are affected by convulsive behavior, especially when it is difficult to find an online shop on various social media is an example of the modern era. Students with convulsive behavior require regulation, both internal control, and control over the behavior.

External influence arises within each person, one of which is faith or belief, whereas external control is the support or power of others or the climate. Religion can regulate specific human actions, such as consumer behavior. Consumptive relates to the actions of customers who use a quantity of money more significant than the demand of their community for products and services that are not necessary needs (Tambunan, 2007)

Consumptive conduct is the action of consumer goods that are absent or not required, especially in response to the consumption of secondary goods that are not required (see Grace of the Heart: 2015). More specifically, the consumer explains the desire to share goods that are less needed to achieve maximum satisfaction (Jumiati, 2009). Social conduct factors (Lina and Rosyid, 1997) note many facets of customer behavior.

1. Impelling purchases are immediate purchases by consumers without a clear basis for consideration.
2. Excessive sales are transactions by customers that are not focused on specific desires and appear to be a waste of resources.
3. Unreasonable transactions are unreasonable actions by customers, restricted mainly to pursuing the pattern Effect of customer behavior.
4. Economic patterns of consumer behavior that can cause financial problems for families, especially for less well-off families.

The psychological impact of a consumptive lifestyle can cause a consumptive lifestyle participant to become addicted to learning in such a way that he or she will not be able to distinguish between wants and needs until the individual can eventually drop out or feel inferior in order to avoid the consumptive impact on students of the need to exercise self-control over consumer behavior, one of which is the influence of religion. Consummative conduct is defined as purchasing or obtaining an unnecessary commodity that is absent or not required or induced the presence of incentives, rewards, or Popularity to achieve full gratification.

Although religiosity is a sign, a principle, a philosophy, a conviction that is a fundamental human characteristic that acts as a direction or instruction to human beings who order themselves to behave in compliance with the degree of obedience to God as a knowledge of an individual's relationship with God, religiosity has many purposes, one of which is a transforming feature, which is a tool of worship that can turn a person's personal or collective existence into a new one, according to the beliefs of the worship he professes. The position of faith can not be distinguished from that of Islam. Faith becomes an essential benchmark because faith provides a worldview that tends to influence human personality, namely behavior, lifestyle, taste, and attitudes towards people. Faith has a significant impact on the nature, quantity, and quality of consumption both in material and spiritual satisfaction (Pratama, 2015).

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